

Density functional study on spectroscopic properties of *meso*-phenyl and 3,5-diaryl substituted BODIPY dyes

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Manuscript received online 27 May 2014, accepted 15 October 2016

Abstract : The molecular structures, infrared and electronic absorption spectra of four *meso*-phenyl and 3,5-diaryl substituted BODIPY dyes, A to D, were investigated theoretically using the gradient-corrected density functional theory B3LYP method. The dependence of spectra with the molecular and electronic structures was investigated on the basis of time-dependent density functional theory (TD-DFT) computations with the B3LYP hybrid functional under 6-31+G*, 6-31G and 6-31G* in different solvents. The vibrational and transition modes of spectra were explored in terms of their microscopic origin. According to structure analysis, the intersection angles of BODIPY core with *meso*-phenyl were estimated 59–61° and the angles of BODIPY ring with 3,5-diaryl groups were evaluated 38–62°. The UV-Vis spectra were in good accordance with the experimental values. The maximum wavelengths of BODIPYs arose from S₀→S₁ transition which stemmed from HOMO to LUMO ($\pi_{\text{BODIPY core}} \rightarrow \pi_{\text{BODIPY core}}^*$). However, the maximum absorptions of four BODIPYs increased inconspicuously with magnified the 3,5-diaryl substitution that caused by nonradioactive loss of energy via rotation around the C-Ar bonds to preventing free rotation. The solvation energies of four BODIPYs are -26.26, -30.39, -34.1, -27.58 kJ/mol, respectively.

Keywords : BODIPY dyes, electronic absorption spectra, density functional theory, solvation energy.

Introduction

Nowadays, the notable advantages of 4,4-difluoro-4-bora-3a,4a-diaza-s-indacene (hereafter abbreviated to BODIPY)¹⁻³ derivatives such as high fluorescence quantum yields, high extinction coefficients, fluorescence emission in the long wavelength region, good stability towards light and chemicals⁴. The crucial reasons that have ensured their wide use in light harvesting, energy transport, sensing, fluorescent switches, potential candidates, biological labeling, solid-state solar concentrators, photodynamic therapy agents, biological imaging, and so on^{5,6}. Numerous BODIPY analogues based on pyrromethenes, diketones, pyridomethenes, subphthalocyanines, subporphyrins, azobenzenes, and others have been explored after the first member of this set was reported as early as 1968 by Treibs and Kreuzer⁷. But most studies concerned with BODIPYs mainly focused on ex-

periments, and theoretical investigations for BODIPY dyes were seldom reported over the past few decades.

Density functional theory (DFT)^{8,9} is a popular quantum mechanical modeling method applied in physics and chemistry to investigate the ground-state properties of a chemical system. Within the DFT framework, the time-dependent density functional theory (TD-DFT)¹⁰⁻¹⁴ method can further provide reliable molecular orbital information relating to electronic excitations. In recent years, the DFT or TD-DFT method has frequently been used to calculate molecular structure, electronic structure, IR spectra, UV-Vis spectra and molecular orbital information with rather satisfactory results obtained¹⁵⁻¹⁷. With the continued development of software and computer techniques, the TD-DFT method can presently be fitted for medium-sized molecules up to 200 atoms¹⁸. The molecular structure, absorption spectra and molecular orbital of

molecules can be calculated by quantum theory workers using DFT and TD-DFT, respectively^{19,20}.

meso-Phenyl and 3,5-diaryl substituted BODIPY dyes have been reported in 1998^{1,21,22}. The substituted 3,5-diaryl units extend the conjugation of the BODIPY systems. Both the absorption and emission maxima of 3,5-diaryl substituted BODIPYs are shifted to longer wavelengths ($\lambda_{\text{max-emis}} = 588\text{--}626\text{ nm}$)¹. In the present work, the molecular structure, electronic structure and spectroscopic properties of four emblematical *meso*-phenyl and 3,5-diaryl substituted BODIPY dyes were investigated using density functional calculations. In order to compare with the experimental results, the solvent effects and substituent effects on UV-Vis spectra were investigated, respectively. Molecular geometry structure analysis showed that the intersection angles between BODIPY core and *meso*-phenyl were estimated 59~61°, and the angles between BODIPY ring and 3,5-diaryl units were evaluated to be 38~62°. These angles were associated with the size of 3,5-substituted groups and the substitution position on 3,5-diaryl substituted groups. The largest absorption wavelengths come from $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ electronic transition, stemmed from HOMO to LUMO ($\pi_{\text{BODIPY core}} \rightarrow \pi_{\text{BODIPY core}}^*$). The maximum absorptions increased inconspicuously with magnified 3,5-substituted groups, this result may be caused by nonradioactive loss of energy via rotation around the C-Ar bonds. The methoxy group of compound C can push electronic and promote the liquidity on the intramolecular energy transfer, so its maximum absorption wavelength is the largest in the four compounds.

Computational details :

The structures of the *meso*-phenyl and 3,5-diaryl substituted BODIPY dyes (A~D) are shown in Fig. 1. The popular quantum chemistry software Gaussian 09W²³ was used to implement the present computational study. The lowest-energy conformer was fully optimized without the symmetric restraint using the DFT^{24,25} method combined with the Becke, three-parameter, Lee-Yang-Parr (B3LYP) exchange-correlation functional^{14,26,27}. Next, their infrared spectra (IR) were calculated under the B3LYP/6-31+G* level²⁸ in gas and CHCl_3 . In order to compare with the experimental data, the electronically excited states

Fig. 1. Molecular structures of BODIPY derivatives A~D.

involving the first 30 excited states of BODIPYs A~D were calculated using the TD-DFT²⁹ method under the B3LYP/6-31+G* level²⁸ in gas, CHCl_3 , EtOH respectively. In addition, the UV-Vis spectra of BODIPYs A~D were calculated under 6-31G³⁰ and 6-31G*^{31,32} in CHCl_3 and EtOH, respectively. In all calculations, squeezed self-consistent field (SCF)³³ convergence standards were adopted, the self-consistent reaction field (SCRf) method and polarized continuum model (PCM)^{34,35} were used to optimize their geometries and calculate their UV-Vis spectra under the different basis set according to the different solvent.

According to the calculated absorption frequency values, infrared vibrational strength, the IR spectra were simulated with peaks of 15 cm^{-1} as half-width having Lorentzian characteristics³⁶. On the basis of transition dipole strengths and absorption maxima, the UV-Vis spectra were fitted with a Lorentzian linear shape of 10 nm half-width. Optimized molecular structures and the intersection angle of BODIPY core with *meso*-phenyl or substituted 3,5-diaryl are shown in Fig. 2. The IR spectra calculated under the B3LYP/6-31+G* level in gas and CHCl_3 are shown in Fig. 3 and Table 1. The UV-Vis spectra calculated under different basis set in different solvent are shown in Figs. 4, 5 and Table 2. Three-dimensional diagrams of the highest occupied molecular orbitals (HOMOs) and lowest unoccupied molecular orbitals (LUMOs) with isocontours of 0.01 a.u. are shown in Fig. 6.

Results and discussion

Molecular conformation :

As shown in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2, the structures of A~D have the analogous BODIPY skeletons except most diaryl

Fig. 2. The optimized molecular structures of the BODIPYs A~D and the intersection angles of BODIPY core and *meso*-phenyl or 3,5-diaryl substituted under the B3LYP/6-31+G* level.

functional groups located on the BODIPY ring at C-3 and C-5. The intersection angles of BODIPY core with *meso*-phenyl and different 3,5-diaryl substituted units were different. The intersection angles between BODIPY core and *meso*-phenyl were estimated 59 to 61° and the angles diminished about 1° that accompanied the larger 3,5-diaryl substituted. Consistent with this, the angles between BODIPY ring and 3,5-diaryl groups were evaluated 38 to 62°. But the angle diminished 1~8° followed the diverse 3,5-*para*-diaryl substitutions especially in compound C and D. Contrarily, the angles were magnified about 18° if they were substituted by 3,5-*ortho*-diaryl groups at C-3 and C-5, like compound B. Such differences were caused by the nonradioactive loss of energy via rotation around the C-Ar bonds in 3,5-*ortho*-substituted compound, especially the large naphthalene group.

Infrared spectra :

The DFT method is frequently used to determine structures and harmonic vibrational frequencies of organic

molecules, and is considered as a powerful tool for the prediction of IR spectra. The IR spectra peaks of the BODIPYs were assigned primarily based on simulated results. The calculated IR spectra of BODIPYs A~D were shown in Fig. 3 and Table 1. Furthermore, the solvation energies of four BODIPYs were -26.26, -30.39, -34.1, -27.58 kJ/mol calculated from the results calculated under B3LYP/6-31+G* and PCM-B3LYP/6-31+G* (in CHCl₃). All compounds exhibited about 10 absorption peaks with both vibration and flexural vibration frequencies were corrected by the factor 0.962. The symbol ν was used to assign the spectral peaks of BODIPY A~D (Fig. 2(A) to 2(D)).

There was a single peak about 3000 cm⁻¹ in each calculated IR spectrum of BODIPYs A~D, and it originated from $\nu_s(\text{C}=\text{CH})$, $\nu_{as}(\text{C}=\text{CH})$ vibration. Only compound C has one weak peak caused by $\nu_{as}(\text{CH}_3)$, $\nu_s(\text{CH}_3)$ vibration around 2900 cm⁻¹. From 1400 to 1600 cm⁻¹, several strong peaks ν_2 - ν_5 were contributed by a group

Fig. 3. Simulated IR spectra of BODIPY dyes A ~ D at the B3LYP/6-31+G* and PCM-B3LYP/6-31+G* level (in CHCl₃).

of close vibration absorptions originated from $\nu_s(\text{C}=\text{C})$, $\nu_{as}(\text{C}=\text{C})$, $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ vibrations. In vicinity of 1260 cm^{-1} , some different intensity peaks were assigned to $\nu_s(\text{N}-\text{B})$ and $\nu_{as}(\text{N}-\text{B})$, etc. in BODIPY core. Moreover, the absorption peaks come from $\delta(\text{C}=\text{CH})$, $\nu(\text{B}-\text{F})$ and $\nu(\text{N}-\text{B})$ vibration between 1200 and 1000 were strong. Near 900 cm^{-1} , peaks ν_8 – ν_{10} were attributed to BF_2 unit extensions and showed a faintish absorption in IR spectrum, such as $\nu(\text{B}-\text{F})$ and $\nu(\text{N}-\text{B})$. From 650 to 800 cm^{-1} , the weak peaks originated from $\gamma(\text{C}=\text{CH})$ vibrancy.

The above discussions show that BODIPYs A ~ D have identifiable infrared spectral areas. IR spectra were well matched with their molecular structures, and the values had not exhibited obvious differences between the B3LYP/6-31+G* and PCM-B3LYP/6-31+G* level. According to the IR spectra analysis, they may conclude as follows :

these class BODIPY dyes have identifiable spectrum areas. For example, $\nu_s(\text{C}=\text{CH})$ and $\nu_{as}(\text{C}=\text{CH})$ vibrations shown a medium intensity in IR spectra occurred above 3000 cm^{-1} . The $\nu_s(\text{C}=\text{C})$, $\nu_{as}(\text{C}=\text{C})$ and $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ vibrancy displayed strong IR absorbance emerged from 1400 to 1600 cm^{-1} . And the $\delta(\text{C}=\text{CH})$ or $\nu(\text{N}-\text{B})$ vibration was found from 900 to 1200 cm^{-1} . $\gamma(\text{C}=\text{CH})$ vibrancy occurred from 650 to 800 cm^{-1} .

Ultraviolet-Visible spectroscopy :

All calculated UV-Vis spectra are shown in Figs. 4, 5 and Table 2. The molecular orbital energy diagrams and isodensity surface plots of the highest occupied molecular orbitals (HOMOs) and lowest unoccupied molecular orbitals (LUMOs) of BODIPYs are shown in Fig. 6. Fig. 4 depicts the evolution for the UV-Vis spectra of BODIPYs A ~ D calculated under the B3LYP/6-31+G* levels in

Table 1. Calculated IR and spectra of BODIPYs A ~ D under the PCM-B3LYP/6-31+G* level (in CHCl₃)

BODIPYs	Mode ^a	ν (cm ⁻¹)	<i>I</i> (km/mol)	Assign	Mode ^a	ν (cm ⁻¹)	<i>I</i> (km/mol)	Assign
A	ν_1	3092	22.9	$\nu_s(\text{C}=\text{CH})$	ν_5	1263	318.9	$\nu_{as}(\text{N-B})$
		3089	39.7	$\nu_s(\text{C}=\text{CH})$	ν_6	1122	974.1	$\nu_{as}(\text{N-B})$
		3081	67.4	$\nu_{as}(\text{C}=\text{CH})$		1116	111.9	$\nu_s(\text{N-B})$
	ν_2	1521	1567.3	$\nu_{as}(\text{C}=\text{C})$	ν_7	1055	748.8	$\delta(\text{C}=\text{CH})$
		1510	172.3	$\nu_s(\text{C}=\text{C})$		1027	179.7	$\delta(\text{C}=\text{CH})$
	ν_3	1459	116.2	$\nu_{as}(\text{C}=\text{N})$	ν_8	940	90.9	$\nu_s(\text{B-F})$
		1455	608	$\nu_s(\text{C}=\text{C})$		914	89.9	$\nu_s(\text{B-F})$
	ν_4	1373	192.8	$\nu_{as}(\text{C}=\text{N}, \text{C})$	ν_9	746	92.1	$\gamma(\text{C}=\text{CH})$
	ν_5	1284	195.9	$\nu_{as}(\text{C}=\text{C})$	ν_{10}	706	108.7	$\gamma(\text{C}=\text{CH})$
		1278	204.7	$\nu_{as}(\text{C}=\text{C})$				
B	ν_1	3087	26.9	$\nu_s(\text{C}=\text{CH})$	ν_5	1284	105.9	$\nu_{as}(\text{C}=\text{C})$
		3083	68.1	$\nu_{as}(\text{C}=\text{CH})$		1266	512.4	$\nu_{as}(\text{N-B})$
		3082	42.1	$\nu_{as}(\text{C}=\text{CH})$	ν_6	1134	125.6	$\delta(\text{C}=\text{CH})$
	ν_2	1562	100.7	$\nu_{as}(\text{C}=\text{C}, \text{Ph})$		1123	244.7	$\nu_{as}(\text{N-B})$
		1523	1617.3	$\nu_{as}(\text{C}=\text{C})$		1090	1181.2	$\nu_{as}(\text{N-B})$
		1510	201.1	$\nu_{as}(\text{C}=\text{C})$	ν_7	1036	245.0	$\delta(\text{C}=\text{CH})$
	ν_3	1473	95.3	$\nu_{as}(\text{C}=\text{C})$		1013	145.9	$\nu_s(\text{B-F})$
		1466	537.3	$\nu_{as}(\text{C}=\text{N})$	ν_8	949	169.6	$\nu_s(\text{B-F}, \text{N-B})$
	ν_4	1370	199.1	$\nu_{as}(\text{C}=\text{N}, \text{C})$	ν_9	759	177.9	$\gamma(\text{C}=\text{CH})$
		1366	227.1	$\nu_{as}(\text{C}=\text{N}, \text{C})$				
C	ν_1	3108	20.4	$\nu_s(\text{C}=\text{CH})$	ν_6	1264	314.4	$\nu_{as}(\text{N-B})$
		3092	27.4	$\nu_s(\text{C}=\text{CH})$		1241	675.8	$\nu(\text{C}-\text{C})$
		3086	29.4	$\nu_{as}(\text{C}=\text{CH})$		1237	477.5	$\nu(\text{C}-\text{C})$
	ν_2	2998	42.7	$\nu_{as}(\text{CH}_3)$	ν_7	1206	145.1	$\nu_{as}(\text{C}=\text{N})$
		2926	88.2	$\nu_s(\text{CH}_3)$	ν_8	1168	307.2	$\delta(\text{C}=\text{CH})$
		2925	102.7	$\nu_s(\text{CH}_3)$		1165	224.7	$\delta(\text{C}=\text{CH})$
	ν_3	1589	428.5	$\nu_s(\text{C}=\text{C})$	ν_9	1122	940.9	$\nu_{as}(\text{N-B})$
	ν_4	1524	1450.1	$\nu_{as}(\text{C}=\text{C})$		1112	64.1	$\nu_a(\text{N-B})$
		1501	117.9	$\nu_{as}(\text{C}=\text{C})$		1056	858.2	$\delta(\text{C}=\text{CH})$
	ν_5	1459	450.8	$\nu_{as}(\text{C}=\text{C})$	ν_{10}	777	111.2	$\gamma(\text{C}=\text{CH})$
1451		1150.5	$\nu_{as}(\text{C}=\text{C})$	ν_{11}	699	88.4	$\gamma(\text{C}=\text{CH})$	
D	ν_1	3093	24.6	$\nu_s(\text{C}=\text{CH})$	ν_6	1285	174.5	$\nu_{as}(\text{C}=\text{C})$
		3087	27.5	$\nu_{as}(\text{C}=\text{CH})$		1280	187.4	$\nu_{as}(\text{C}=\text{C})$
		3082	20.2	$\nu_{as}(\text{C}=\text{CH})$		1262	265.5	$\nu_{as}(\text{N-B})$
	ν_2	1585	111.6	$\nu_s(\text{C}=\text{C})$	ν_7	1193	273	$\nu(\text{C}-\text{F})$
		1584	92.3	$\nu_s(\text{C}=\text{C})$		1192	177.9	$\nu(\text{C}-\text{F})$
	ν_3	1524	1452	$\nu_s(\text{C}=\text{C})$	ν_8	1145	114.2	$\delta(\text{C}=\text{CH})$
		1497	119.9	$\nu_{as}(\text{C}=\text{C})$		1119	1087.2	$\nu_{as}(\text{N-B})$
	ν_4	1460	323.1	$\nu_{as}(\text{C}=\text{C})$	ν_9	1055	628.9	$\delta(\text{C}=\text{CH})$
		1453	869.4	$\nu_{as}(\text{C}=\text{C})$	ν_{10}	952	82	$\nu_a(\text{N-B})$
	ν_5	1413	168.2	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$	ν_{11}	778	107.9	$\gamma(\text{C}=\text{CH})$
1406		147	$\nu_a(\text{N-B})$	ν_{12}	699	79.3	$\gamma(\text{C}=\text{CH})$	

^a ν in cm⁻¹, IR in km/mol. Calculated frequencies have been corrected by a factor of 0.962. The symbol ν is a stretching mode, ν_{as} is an asymmetrical stretch, and ν_s is a symmetrical stretch. Furthermore, δ stands for a bending mode and γ is a rocking mode.

Fig. 4. Electronic absorption spectra for BODIPY derivatives A ~ D under the B3LYP/6-31+G* level in different solvents.

different solvent. And Fig. 5 depicts the evolution for the UV-Vis spectra of BODIPYs A ~ D calculated under the B3LYP/6-31G* and B3LYP/6-31G levels in different solvent. All of them exhibit three absorption bands (I, II, III) between 200 to 600 nm, bands II and III were weak in intensity, while band I was provided with the maximum strong absorption peaks that emerged in the vicinity of 500 to 550 nm.

In Figs. 4, 5 and Table 2, bands I rendered a maximum-strength absorption peak in UV-Vis spectrum which originated from the $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ transition induced by HOMO to LUMO ($\pi_{\text{BODIPY core}} \rightarrow \pi_{\text{BODIPY core}}^*$). In Fig. 6, the HOMO charge density crosses the entire BODIPY skeleton, while the LUMO is focused on BODIPY ring (π^*) too. Compared with the experimental values, the calculated largest difference for the maximum absorption wavelengths was ~ 50 nm ($\sim 8.9\%$) and the minimum difference was ~ 4 nm ($\sim 0.7\%$) either calculated under 6-

31+G*, 6-31G* or 6-31G levels in different solvent. This difference between theoretical and experimental results may be caused by two factors. First may be the drawback of the computational methodology employed, such as the imprecise and incomplete functional basis set used. Therefore, if we used a complete basis set for calculations, the calculated value was likely to decrease and showed greater convergence with the experimental values. Another reason was the calculated UV-Vis spectra could be the most stable conformer, but the experimental specimen should consist a mixture containing some sub-stable or unstable conformer. When discussing the UV-Vis spectra, all possible conformers in principle should be considered. The maximum absorption wavelengths of A ~ D have red-shifted after considering the solvent effects calculated under different level in chloroform and EtOH. This was indicated that the BF_2 units can produce hydrogen bonds with solvent molecules and reduce the orbital energy gap (ΔE)

Fig. 5. Electronic absorption spectra for BODIPY derivatives A ~ D at the base functions set 6-31G and 6-31G* in EtOH or CHCl₃ according to the PCM model.

between π and π^* , then led their maximum wavelengths to shift longer.

Bands II of compounds A ~ D appeared between 350 to 450 nm. They were contributed by the $S_0 \rightarrow S_3$ transition. It arose from HOMO-2 to LUMO ($\pi_{\text{naphthalene}}$ and BODIPY core $\rightarrow \pi_{\text{BODIPY core}}^*$) for compound B and the calculated wavelength was 403 nm under the B3LYP/6-31+G* level. In addition, the bands II of BODIPYs A, C, D were stemmed from $S_0 \rightarrow S_2$ transition and originated from HOMO-1 to LUMO ($\pi_{3,5\text{-diaryl substituent}} \rightarrow \pi_{\text{BODIPY ring}}^*$), respectively.

All of bands III were taken on the highest energy area (from 280 to 350 nm). The homologous calculated absorption wavelength of compounds A, C and D were 285, 291 and 280 nm, respectively. They came from $S_0 \rightarrow S_{11}$ electronic transition which originated as HOMO to LUMO+1 ($\pi_{\text{BODIPY core}} \rightarrow \pi_{\text{meso-phenyl}}^*$). Similar to band II, the corresponding absorption wavelength for B is 352

nm that attributed to $S_0 \rightarrow S_6$ transition that stemmed from HOMO-5 to LUMO ($\pi_{\text{BODIPY ring}} \rightarrow \pi_{\text{BODIPY ring}}^*$) as shown in Figs. 4, 5 and Table 2.

In conclusion, four BODIPY derivatives have three absorption bands (I, II, III), the maximum absorption peaks were emerged in the vicinity of 500 to 550 nm and originated from the $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ transition inducing by HOMO to LUMO ($\pi_{\text{BODIPY core}} \rightarrow \pi_{\text{BODIPY core}}^*$). However, they red-shifted obviously and approached to the experimental values after considering the solvent effects under different calculated level. Compound C induced the largest absorption wavelength, this was caused by the methoxy substituent in 3,5-*p*-methoxy phenyl group that can push electronic and promote the liquidity on the intramolecular energy transfer. Conversely, the largest absorption wavelength for compound B red-shifted inconspicuously in proportion with substituting by 3,5-naphthalene. Such differences are widely attributed to 3,5-substituents preventing

Table 2. Calculated UV spectra of BODIPY A ~ D under different level and different solvents

Compound	Method	Band I			Band II			Band III					
		Environment	λ (nm)	f	Expt. ^a	Expt. ^b	Assign ^c	λ (nm)	f	Assign ^c	λ (nm)	f	Assign ^c
A	B3LYP basis set	Environment											
	6-31+G*	Gas	489.8	0.57	555	558	$S_0 \rightarrow S_1$	369.4	0.28	$S_0 \rightarrow S_2$	275.9	0.37	$S_0 \rightarrow S_{11}$
	6-31+G*	CHCl ₃	510.6	0.68			H \rightarrow L($\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$)	376.8	0.44	H \rightarrow L($\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$)	284.8	0.22	H \rightarrow L+I($\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$)
	6-31+G*	EtOH	505.2	0.67				376.2	0.40		283.8	0.55	
	6-31G	CHCl ₃	491.7	0.71				369.1	0.43		267.6	0.33	
	6-31G	EtOH	486.6	0.69				370.4	0.41		268.2	0.53	
	6-31G*	CHCl ₃	500.9	0.69				371.0	0.41		275.6	0.33	
	6-31G*	EtOH	495.9	0.67				372.4	0.39		276.1	0.52	
	6-31+G*	Gas	535.7	0.40	542	550	$S_0 \rightarrow S_1$	403.3	0.23	$S_0 \rightarrow S_2$	326.1	0.13	$S_0 \rightarrow S_2$
	6-31+G*	CHCl ₃	538.1	0.49			H \rightarrow L($\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$)	408.2	0.23	H \rightarrow L($\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$)	352.7	0.23	H \rightarrow L($\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$)
B	6-31+G*	EtOH	532.0	0.53				401.2	0.19		332.1	0.15	
	6-31G	CHCl ₃	531.9	0.50				396.2	0.27		345.0	0.23	
	6-31G	EtOH	523.3	0.50				393.4	0.25		315.5	0.17	
	6-31G*	CHCl ₃	532.5	0.54				401.0	0.22		324.7	0.16	
	6-31G*	EtOH	525.3	0.53				398.4	0.20		325.8	0.17	
	6-31+G*	Gas	524.1	0.59	582	585	$S_0 \rightarrow S_1$	417.7	0.32	$S_0 \rightarrow S_1$	284.1	0.26	$S_0 \rightarrow S_1$
	6-31+G*	CHCl ₃	546.9	0.69			H \rightarrow L($\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$)	424.5	0.46	H \rightarrow L($\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$)	291.4	0.25	H \rightarrow L+I($\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$)
	6-31+G*	EtOH	540.2	0.69				418.2	0.46		289.4	0.48	
	6-31G	CHCl ₃	532.5	0.72				420.6	0.44		275.9	0.39	
	6-31G	EtOH	526.5	0.70				417.8	0.44		274.3	0.56	
C	6-31G*	CHCl ₃	538.2	0.71				418.8	0.43		283.4	0.29	
	6-31G*	EtOH	532.8	0.69				417.0	0.43		280.7	0.50	
	6-31+G*	Gas	487.4	0.58	555	559	$S_0 \rightarrow S_1$	377.8	0.32	$S_0 \rightarrow S_1$	276.7	0.22	$S_0 \rightarrow S_1$
	6-31+G*	CHCl ₃	502.9	0.69			H \rightarrow L($\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$)	381.6	0.47	H \rightarrow L($\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$)	280.4	0.45	H \rightarrow L+I($\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$)
	6-31+G*	EtOH	500.3	0.68				379.9	0.45		282.6	0.50	
	6-31G	CHCl ₃	499.2	0.70				378.8	0.44		274.5	0.47	
	6-31G	EtOH	483.1	0.71				375.1	0.46		268.1	0.51	
	6-31G*	CHCl ₃	499.2	0.70				378.8	0.45		274.5	0.47	
	6-31G*	EtOH	494.0	0.69				378.3	0.43		274.3	0.49	

^aExperimental data were measured in CHCl₃^{1,21,22}. ^bExperimental data were measured in EtOH^{1,21,22}. ^cThe units of λ is nm. H is HOMO and L is LUMO. π and π^* express different groups.

Fig. 6. Molecular orbital energy diagram and isodensity surface plots about the HOMO and LUMO of BODIPY dyes A ~ D calculated at B3LYP/6-31+G* level.

free rotation of the naphthalene group reducing loss of energy from the excited states via non-irradiative molecular motions. The C-Ar free rotations destroyed the conjugation of molecules¹.

Conclusions

In the present work, four emblematical *meso*-phenyl and 3,5-diaryl substituted BODIPY dyes, A ~ D have been studied by optimization of their molecular structures, their corresponding IR, UV-Vis spectra and molecular orbital with energies using a DFT method under B3LYP/6-31+G* level in different environment, and the UV-Vis spectra were studied under 6-31G and 6-31G* basis set in CHCl₃ and EtOH respectively. Their UV-Vis spectra values were well matched with the reported experimental values. Molecular structure analysis suggested that the intersection angles between BODIPY core and *meso*-phenyl were estimated 59 ~ 61°, and the angles between BODIPY ring and 3,5-diaryl units were evaluated 38 ~ 62°. These angles were associated with the size of substituted groups and the substitution position on 3,5-diaryl substituted groups. Calculated IR spectra were in good accordance with their molecular structures and the values had not obvious diffe-

rences between B3LYP/6-31+G* and PCM-B3LYP/6-31+G* (in CHCl₃) levels. Their microscopic origins showed that these representative BODIPYs had a unique identifiable IR spectral areas, such as the $\nu(\text{N-B})$ vibration occurred at 900 to 1200 cm⁻¹. Furthermore, the UV-Vis spectra were good matched with the experimental values too. The largest absorption wavelengths (bands I) came from S₀→S₁ electronic transition, stemmed from HOMO to LUMO ($\pi_{\text{BODIPY core}} \rightarrow \pi_{\text{BODIPY core}^*}$) and occurred obvious red-shift. Calculated results were close to the test values considering the solvent effects. However, the maximum absorption of four BODIPYs didn't increase obviously by magnifying the 3,5-diaryl substituted groups, which attributed to 3,5-substituents preventing free rotation of the phenyl group reducing loss of energy from the excited states via non-irradiative molecular motions.

Acknowledgement

This work is supported by the General Program of Yunnan Provincial Education Department (2015Y455), the Chemistry of Key Construction Disciplines for Master

Degree Program in Yunnan (No. HXZ1303), the Educational Reform Program of Honghe University (No. JJG1412), the National Natural Science Foundation of China (61361002) and the Scientific Research Foundation of Education Department of Yunnan Province (No. 2013FZ121).

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